

Critical Asset Lifecycle Optimisation: Predictive Resilience in National Infrastructure

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Abstract—Water is a fundamental necessity, the people of Tanzania know this yet the lack of even distribution of fresh water sources makes it hard to be perceived as such. To optimize the utilization of the accessible water resources, it is crucial to establish an efficient water management system, which entails comprehending the operational status of the available water points. This study concentrates on the deployment of four machine learning classification models to predict whether a given water point is functional, needs reparation, or is non-functionality based on its provided attributes. Furthermore, three research questions were formulated to support the analysis, investigating the correlation between individual attributes and the water point’s functionality, as well as the interrelationships among various attributes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this project is to train a machine learning (ML) model to effectively predict the degree of functionality of a water pump based off its given attributes, such that if deployed, it could aid the Tanzanian Ministry of Water [1] to issue repairs and handle non-functional water pumps more effectively and at a reduced cost. The data originates from Taarifa water point Dashboard [2], and the Tanzania ministry of water. Taarifa is an open-source platform which aggregates data regarding water points based off crowd-sourced reports.

A. Research Questions

- 1) Exploratory: Are older water points (construction_year) more prone to being non-functional or requiring repairs?
 - The logical inference here being that over time machinery tend to deteriorate.
 - a) Does water quality (water_quality) affect functionality? A sub-research question that explores the effect of water quality on the potential mineral build-up in the piping structure thus having an effect onto the functionality.
- 2) Inferential: Are water points located in higher altitude areas (gps_height) more likely to have lower water availability (amount_tsh)? As altitude increases, pressure decreases meaning that the pump will have to work harder, resulting in potentially lower water availability.

B. Data Analysis Preliminary Findings

The dataset contains information regarding 59,400 water points in Tanzania. For each water point, 39 attributes have

been identified:

Fig. 2. illustrates initial measures of central tendency (mean, mode and median), measures of variability (standard and deviation and quartile split) and the general distribution of the data. This initial description of the data set also highlights some potential issues and outliers, for instance if we observe the max recorded value of the amount_tsh we can see it far exceeds the mean and the values of the third quartile illustrating that it may need to be handled as it could increase error variance, decrease normality and even impact the assumption of regression when considering its implication on the models.

	amount_tsh	gps_height	longitude	latitude	num_private	region_code	district_code	population	construction_year
count	59363.000000	59363.000000	59363.000000	5.936300e+04	59363.000000	59363.000000	59363.000000	59363.000000	59363.000000
mean	317.848371	666.713778	34.098134	-5.709559e+00	0.474437	15.295487	5.631572	180.022118	1301.463150
std	2998.498105	693.131418	6.515617	2.943539e+00	12.240037	17.592766	9.636200	471.607687	951.362721
min	0.000000	-90.000000	0.000000	-1.164944e+01	0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.000000	0.000000	33.095232	-8.541951e+00	0.000000	5.000000	2.000000	0.000000	0.000000
50%	0.000000	370.000000	34.910385	-5.023920e+00	0.000000	12.000000	3.000000	25.000000	1986.000000
75%	20.000000	1320.000000	37.179574	-3.326925e+00	0.000000	17.000000	6.000000	215.000000	2004.000000
max	350000.000000	2770.000000	40.345193	-2.000000e+08	1776.000000	99.000000	80.000000	30500.000000	2013.000000

Fig. 1. Description statistics of the Taarifa dataset using .describe()

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A group of students at Minerva University [3], undertook the same challenge as us, that of using ML to determine the functionality of water pumps around Tanzania using the same dataset from Taarifa. When it came to pre-processing, the students decided to weed out the features of the dataset which they deemed “irrelevant” to the prediction model. [4] This data-wrangling was done manually by the team, this means that personal bias was involved when determining which features mattered and which did not. This subjective approach may not have been the best one as outlined by A. Stark [4], because it led to discarding half of all the available features, some of which potentially may have been informative and may have had a causal relationship with the functionality of the water points. A more holistic approach would have been to generate a correlation matrix to determine the irrelevant features. Other approaches were included pertaining to columns and categorical values, although, no mentions of pre-processing that tackles missing values, outliers or

duplicates in the data points were present.

A. Stark and his team explored numerous models for this classification problem including: logistic regression, decision trees, random forests and k-nearest neighbours. Out of all the used modelling techniques used, the team found the most success with decision trees and Random forests with classification accuracy scores exceeding 70%. On the other hand, for KNN and logistic regression the success rate hovered at 52%, this score remained effectively unchanged for all numbers of neighbours ranging from 2 to 9. The team believes this low performance on the KNN could be traced back to the lack of adequate pre-processing. Moreover, random forest and decision trees approaches are known to be robust to noise and outliers [5], which may be linked to their increased success.

Castineira utilised SpeedWise ML (SWML), an AutoML solution, to generate accurate predictive models such as knowing the water pump functionality in Tanzania. [6] This methodology was chosen as it provided means of providing a smart, automated approach to ML that can generate accurate models very easily and quickly, such as the Tanzania dataset (that has more than 2.3 million cells). Further benefits include many tasks being automated such as data cleaning, feature engineering, model selection, and hyperparameter tuning. This also means that automation done by Castineira may result in a lack of transparency and interpretability, making it difficult understanding how the model arrived at its predictions. Furthermore, from a general perspective, SWML may not be able to handle all types of data therefore requiring significant tuning and customization to be effective. [6]

A. Clean Data

Castineria's work does not discuss approaches to other methodologies, so studies of other approaches will be conducted. Castineria highlights the existence of incomplete features (i.e., features with missing data). This problem is solved by using binary encoding, for categorical encoding, and a combination of KNN and random forest for data imputation. Moreover, Castineria leverages SWML AutoPilot option to automatically deal with most of the data pre-processing issues to generate a well-condition dataset. He emphasises how the process appropriately splits the data into training, validation and test sets, which the AutoPilot feature facilities in 'a smart way'. Though this is true, considerations such as this process hiding important details and nuances that may affect the accuracy and reliability of the final model.

B. ML Model Building/Optimization

Castineria mentions SWML allows users to choose from a range of ML models. With down-sides considered, this aspect can be deemed excusable, as justification of using the SpeedWise ML technique resulted in a succession rate of 90% accuracy in predicting functionality of water pumps for training.

III. METHODOLOGY

Two different approaches were conducted by the researchers at each stage of the project: pre-processing, data analysis and classification models.

A. Data Pre-Processing

In order to conduct two different approaches for pre-processing, two copies of the data-set were created: `df_ab` and `df_z`. When it came to pre-processing, the following areas were addressed:

- Duplicated data entries
- Missing values (NaN values)
- Outliers and placeholders

1) *Duplicated Data*: The Pandas library provides an effective method for duplicate data identification, this method was used on both data-sets. The result concluded that no duplicate data was present.

2) *Missing Values*: Bukhari handled missing values in the data set by directly removing any entries that contained at least one NaN value. This approach ensured that the remaining data accurately represented the intended information and maintained the overall integrity of the data set, minimizing the influence of biased or skewed information.

Ali used imputation to handle the missing values. Brief EDA revealed all missing values were from nominal features [7] therefore median imputation was deemed most appropriate as calculating a mean was infeasible due to the non-numerical nature of the values. Data imputation preserves sample size and statistical power of all available data. [8]

3) *Outliers and Placeholders*: Both Ali and Bukhari identified extreme outliers by removing values beyond the 95th and 5th percentiles.

To identify placeholders, Bukhari considered only the numerical data that was used to plot a box-plot representation for each attribute to visualise the distribution. Box plots provided a visual summary of data distribution that allowed for quick identification of outliers/placeholders in the data set. [9] Mean imputation was selected to handle outliers, preserving all data points and maintaining statistical power. [10] Bukhari's assumption of missing values being completely random allowed for an unbiased estimate of the mean. Imputing missing values with the mean incorporates them into the variable's statistical properties, reducing potential biases from excluding missing values. [11]

Ali also focused exclusively on the numerical data. Histogram representation was utilized for each of the considered attributes to visually analyze the data distribution. Histograms facilitate identification of outliers, general tendencies, and skewed distributions. [12] Ali chose median imputation chosen for its ability to handle outliers and preserve data distribution, in addition brief EDA revealed that all missing values were from nominal features thus fortifying the need for median imputation.

Neglecting these placeholders diminishes attribute significance in models, leading to poorer performance [13].

B. Feature Selection

Bukhari's performed feature selection prior to one-hot encoding for feature engineering. This order of operations was necessary to avoid the challenges posed by the exponential increase in attribute dimensionality, if one-hot encoding had been applied before feature selection then Bukhari would have had to manually perform EDA on thousands of attributes. In contrast, Ali performed feature engineering before feature selection to ensure a numerically encoded data set suitable for extracting the most relevant features using a predictive model.

1) *Exploratory Data Analysis*: Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) is a manual examination undertaken by Bukhari to identify and exclude attributes deemed irrelevant to the research question and the determination of water point functionality. [14] Alongside relevant features, this approach also aimed to eliminate redundant attributes. EDA was selected as it facilitates the identification of conspicuous areas and enhances comprehension of data patterns, including the detection of outliers and anomalous events.

2) *Tree-Based*: Ali employed a Tree-Based method to select relevant features, specifically using a Random Forest (RF) Classifier [15]. This approach leverages the inherent feature selection capability of tree-based predictive ML models, where each feature is assigned a weight based on its impact on the prediction model. A tree-based approach is highly accurate, as it effectively predicts outcomes based on patterns in the data, it generalizes well to new data by applying learned knowledge, and it is interpretable.

C. Feature Engineering

1) *One-Hot Encoding*: Bukhari utilized one-hot encoding to convert categorical data into a numerical format compatible with the classification models. [16]. This method adds binary features to represent categorical variables, preserving their categorical information without introducing additional computation. By employing one-hot encoding, the categorical attributes are accurately represented within the classification framework, allowing for meaningful analysis while maintaining the integrity of the original data.

2) *Target-Based Encoding*: Ali used target-based encoding; a technique that encodes categorical variables based on their relationship with the target variable without increasing dimensionality. [?] It incorporates information about the target into the encoding process thus allowing the classification models to capture the correlation between the categorical variable and the target, in turn resulting in stronger performance.

D. Classification Models

Four diverse classification models, namely K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naive Bayes, Random Forest (RF), and Decision Tree, were applied to the data sets to observe their impact on classification outcomes. Each model is based on a different algorithmic principle: KNN utilizes an instance-based algorithm, Naive Bayes employs probabilistic methods, RF leverages ensemble techniques, and Decision Tree adopts a non-linear tree-based approach. This approach allows for the

evaluation of performance across various models, promoting a comprehensive assessment of their effectiveness. (see § V.D)

1) *KNN*: In order to determine the optimal value that would yield the highest accuracy, K values ranging from 0-7 were tested. The selection of KNN as the chosen method was motivated by its inherent resilience to outliers and its simplicity. [17]

2) *Random Forest & Decision Tree*: Both RF and Decision Tree models possess the capability to effectively handle high-dimensional data, exhibit robustness against over-fitting, and demonstrate high predictive accuracy due to their underlying tree-based algorithms. [15] Notably, the key distinction lies in the fact that Random Forest, in addition to its tree-based approach, amalgamates multiple decision trees to collectively arrive at more precise and accurate decisions.

3) *Naive Bayes (GaussianNB)*: Naive Bayes exhibits robustness in the presence of irrelevant features. Naive Bayes demonstrates versatility in accommodating both continuous and discrete data types, allowing for seamless integration of various types of variables in the classification process. [18]

E. Approach to Answering Research Questions

Initially, visual data analysis was used as a means to obtain preliminary insights and potential outcomes in response to the research question. For question 1 a bar chart was utilized due to its capacity to clearly represent the data distribution, thereby enabling an assessment of whether age exerted an influence on functionality. For question 1a, (see § I.A.1), stacked bar charts were employed to effectively visualize the relationship between water quality and functionality. This visualization method facilitated the distinct separation of various water qualities and allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the proportions of the three functionality statuses across different water quality categories. Lastly, to address the inferential question 2, a scatter plot was chosen as it possesses inherent capabilities to elucidate any existing correlations between variables. This selection aimed to uncover and visually represent potential relationships or associations between the variables of interest.

Subsequently, ML and statistical models were employed to obtain definitive answers and draw conclusive conclusions. Logistic regression is used to assess if older water points are more prone to being non-functional or needing repairs. It models the relationship between water point age (independent variable) and functional status (dependent variable), estimating the probability of non-functionality based on age. The chi-squared test assesses the association between water quality and water point functionality, both categorical variables. It determines if there is a significant association between the two and helps answer whether water quality affects functionality.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \left(\frac{O_i - E_i^2}{E_i} \right)$$

Linear regression is used to determine if higher altitude areas have lower water availability. It models the relationship

between water availability (dependent variable) and altitude (independent variable). The model assesses the linear association, providing insights into the direction and strength of the relationship.

IV. RESULTS

Bukhari’s data was reduced by 53% (59,400 to 27,813 rows) by dropping entries with missing values. Ali’s data set imputed all 46,094 missing values with medians, keeping the same data set size. Both researchers discarded 2611 and 5549 entries, respectively, when dealing with outliers, reflecting their different approaches to handling missing values. In Figure 2, mean imputation on Bukhari’s data set caused a shift in the longitude attribute’s value distribution from 40-0 to 40-30.

Fig. 2. Box plot depiction of the effects of mean imputation on longitude data distribution

Following median imputation, histograms revealed a distinct outlier at 0 in attributes `amount_tsh`, `population`, `num_private`, `longitude`, `gps_height`, and `construction_year`. Further investigation confirmed these instances as missing values. To address this, all 0 values were replaced with the corresponding attribute’s median using median imputation. Figure 3 demonstrates this for the `construction_year` attribute, enhancing visualization by accurately representing the range of values (1960 to 2010) on the x-axis instead of 0 to 2000.

Fig. 3. Histogram depiction of the effects of median imputation on construction year data distribution

A. Visual Data Analysis & Research Questions

1) *Question 1:* As a preliminary step, minor feature engineering was performed on both data sets by replacing all

values in the `construction_year` attribute with the age of the water point, calculated through a simple procedure. Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of water points across different age ranges, revealing that a substantial portion of functional water points is concentrated within the 0-30 years age range. This observation supports the hypothesis that older water points are more susceptible to requiring repairs and becoming non-functional.

Fig. 4. Bar chart distribution of the number of functional water points by age.

Logistic regression was applied to finalise an answer to the question. Target variables were encoded as 0, 1, and 2, representing non-functional, requiring repair, and functional statuses, respectively. Logistic regression interpreted this ordinal encoding as a measure of success, where 0 denoted an unfavorable outcome and 2 indicated a favorable outcome. Coefficients were calculated by the logistic regression model for each trained feature. These coefficients reflected the significance of an attribute in predicting a successful outcome, specifically in this case, the functionality of a water point. A negative coefficient suggested that the feature was more likely to contribute to an unsuccessful outcome, indicating non-functionality. Conversely, a positive coefficient indicated a positive correlation between the feature and the model’s prediction success, ultimately resulting in a functional water point. Notably, the analysis revealed that ‘age’ was one of the few features with a positive coefficient of 0.03. This suggested that, according to the model’s prediction, older water points were more likely to be functional. Thus, the research question was answered in the negative, implying that, based on the data analysis, older water points were not more prone to being non-functional or requiring repairs. Figure 5 demonstrated that the majority of features had negative coefficients ranging from -0.01 to 0.

2) *Question 1a:* Figure 6 displays a stacked bar chart illustrating the impact of water quality on water point functionality.

In the `df_ab` data set, around 70% of `coloured` water quality water points are functional, while 25% are non-functional, and the rest require repairs. Conversely, for `salty` water quality water points, 42% are functional, 13% are non-functional, and the rest need repairs. A similar pattern is observed in the `df_z` data set (Figure 6), where approximately 45% of `coloured` water quality water points are functional, 40% are non-functional, and the rest need repairs. For `salty`

Fig. 5. Coefficients of features in logistic regression model, impact of features on predicting the target variable

water quality water points in this data set, 42% are functional, 50% are non-functional, and the rest need repairs.

These findings underscore water quality's influential role in water point functionality, emphasizing its impact.

Fig. 6. Relationship between water quality and functionality across both data sets

A chi-squared test was conducted to examine the potential influence of water quality on the functionality of water pumps. The exploratory analysis of visual data provided compelling evidence suggesting a potential correlation, which prompted the use of the chi-squared test to validate this relationship. The obtained chi-squared statistic of 2128.22% indicated a substantial disparity between the observed and expected frequencies of the relevant features, thereby providing strong evidence supporting the notion that water quality indeed has a significant impact on functionality. Furthermore, the resulting p-value of 0.0 indicated an extremely low likelihood of the observed relationship occurring by chance alone, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and solidifying the conclusion that water quality plays a meaningful role in determining functionality.

3) *Question 2:* Figure 7 portrays a lack of correlation, displaying a somewhat arbitrary distribution of data devoid of any discernible relationship, thereby suggesting a possible absence of correlation between the two aforementioned attributes. Initial visual data analysis yielded inconclusive findings, suggesting the absence of a correlation. To validate this observation, a linear regression analysis was conducted to

Fig. 7. Relationship between water amount (amount TSH) and gps height

assess the relationship between the two variables. The analysis revealed a coefficient of 0.056, indicating an exceedingly weak positive correlation, in addition, Figure 8 illustrates the regression line that represent the strength of the correlation, which appears to be very weak. This suggesting that as water point altitude decreases, there is a slight decrease in water amount, essentially contradicting the initial hypothesis and answering the research question; water points located in higher altitudes are not necessarily more likely to have lower water availability.

Fig. 8. Linear regression line representing the relationship between quantity(amount TSH) and GPS height

B. Feature Selection

The `wpt_name` and `date_recorded` attributes were deemed irrelevant and eliminated. Similarly, the `num_private` attribute lacked proper documentation, with over 97% of values consistently at 28.83, rendering it uninformative. Consequently, it was removed.

To reduce redundancy, only `region_code` and `district_code` were kept among all the geographical location columns. Granular attributes not aligned with the research questions were eliminated. The standardized numeric codes in `region_code` facilitated effortless grouping and analysis by region, making it a preferred choice over the `region` attribute.

Other redundant attributes were eliminated, resulting in an overall removal of 17 out of 39 features in Bukhari’s data set before developing the classification models. This reduction, equivalent to a 43% shrinkage, ensured computational feasibility for the classification models.

Using a Random Forest Classifier, Ali identified the top ten essential features for developing the classification models (Figure 9). [19]. Figure 9 shows the importance scores of the

Fig. 9. Top 10 Feature Importance in Random Forest Classifier

selected features. wpt_name achieved the highest score of 0.34, while funder_encoded scored around 0.02.

C. Feature Engineering

Initially, Bukhari’s data set had 24 attributes, but after one-hot encoding, it expanded by 6868%, resulting in 1742 features.

Figure 10 demonstrates the influence of varying k values on K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model accuracy. Notably, the Bukhari and Ali models exhibit contrasting KNN performance. Bukhari’s optimal k value of 3 achieved an accuracy score of 0.7868%, while Ali’s model reached its highest accuracy score of 0.8797% with k set to 5.

Fig. 10. Effect of different k values across both data sets

D. Classification Model Performance

In Figure 11, the performance scores of four classification models on the two data sets are depicted. Random Forest achieves the highest accuracy scores of 92% and 83% for the Ali and Bukhari data sets, respectively. In contrast, Naive Bayes exhibits the lowest performance, scoring 75% for Ali

and 46% for Bukhari. Notably, the df_z data set consistently outperforms df_ab across all models, demonstrating a consistent trend of higher accuracies. Overall, the classification models exhibit strong performances, with an average score of 86% for Ali and 71% for Bukhari.

Fig. 11. Performance comparison of different classification models

V. DISCUSSION

This section cover the comparison and criticism of various different techniques applied at different stages of the classification process.

A. Pre-processing

Removing rows with NaN values from the data set resulted in the loss of valuable information, decreased representation, reduced statistical power, and introduced bias. This methodology, mentioned in [20] carries the risk of overlooking important data patterns and relationships, leading to sub-optimal accuracy scores for classification models (Section V.D).

Ali’s use of median imputation to handle missing values and placeholders has limitations. It distorts the original data distribution by replacing missing values with the median, reducing variability and artificially narrowing the value range. Additionally, it overlooks interrelationships between attributes, as imputation is performed column-wise.

Bukhari’s mean imputation overlooked categorical data, which requires a different approach as mean imputation is only suitable for numeric values. This resulted in certain attributes with categorical placeholders being neglected. Lastly, Mean imputation assumes missing values are similar to observed data, introducing bias.

Ali and Bukhari only addressed placeholders represented as '0' values, neglecting other potential placeholders and erroneous data. This limitation stems from using simple placeholder identification methods like box plots and histograms. A more thorough EDA could have uncovered hidden placeholders that might improve the classification model performance.

B. Feature Selection and Feature Engineering

Bukhari's subjective feature selection approach allows for better human comprehension and understanding of underlying patterns in the data, but it introduces personal bias into attribute relevance determination. This may result in classification models being biased towards Bukhari's feature selection justifications. In contrast, a tree-based feature selection approach like Ali's tends to perform better by selecting fewer categories (10) compared to Bukhari's approach (17).

Ali's tree-based approach in ML offers objectivity and criticality in feature selection. However, the selection may appear arbitrary to unfamiliar researchers, particularly from a logical and contextual standpoint. For instance, the model identified the water point name as the most relevant feature for predictions, which naturally does not make sense as a water points' name should have no impact on its functionality. However, this choice was driven by the attribute's high cardinality rather than its true predictive value. Tree-based algorithms prioritize features with high variability, and the distinct names of water points contribute to their disproportionate influence in feature selection. Additionally, relying on the RF classifier introduces bias towards specific features, impacting the performance of the classification models.

Bukhari's one-hot encoding process substantially increases the data set's dimensionality by 6868%. This poses challenges for classification models, requiring more computational power and longer processing times, potentially exhausting available resources. One-hot encoding does retain individual category information, unlike target-based encoding, which aggregates data based on its relationship with the target variable through mean computation. High cardinality increases overfitting risk and hampers generalization. It also complicates feature relevance determination, hindering identification of influential predictors.

The successful implementation of target-based encoding in encoding categorical values offers significant benefits, including reduced dimensionality and fewer computational resources required. This approach improves computational model performance, especially when reducing cardinality. Ali's data set benefits from a tree-based feature selection process that further enhances classification model performance. However, it's important to note that target-based encoding can be prone to overfitting as well, as its effectiveness depends on the distribution of the target variable, particularly the `status_group`. Previous research [?] has demonstrated that target-based encoding improves classification models accuracies.

C. Classification Models

Pre-processing, feature selection, and engineering significantly impact model performance. Ali's data set outperformed Bukhari's in all classification models due to the chosen encoding method. The cardinality of the data sets differed between the encoding methods. Lower cardinalities generally yield higher accuracy scores, but this wasn't the case for Bukhari's dataset, which had high cardinality due to one-hot encoding. Figure 11 illustrates the encoding effect on the NB algorithm.

Bukhari's model experienced the largest score discrepancies between the datasets, highlighting the significant impact of cardinality. Figure 11 also illustrates that RF and Decision Tree were shown to retain relatively high accuracy scores even for Bukhari's data set, this is due to their robustness to high cardinality data.

The RF classifier shows significant bias in Ali's results, outperforming other classifiers. This bias is attributed to Ali's customized feature selection process, tailored specifically for the RF classifier, giving it a notable advantage as the top-performing model.

D. Research Questions

Despite the EDA suggesting that the answer to RQ 1 was that water points are more functional when younger, the logistic regression models produced contrasting results. In Figure 9, the coefficients ranged between -0.01 and 0.03, which are extremely low magnitude values this meant that the significance of whether coefficients were positive or negative was overshadowed. Therefore, the suggestion of a higher likelihood of functionality for older water points must be attributed to chance due to the insufficient strength of the Pearson coefficient.

The chi-squared test robustly establishes support for RQ 1a, confirming that water quality significantly affects pump functionality. The graphical representation employed to depict the relationship between water functionality and water quality proved highly effective. It clearly portrayed the proportions of functional water points and visualized trends in functionality across different water types, thereby offering valuable insights into the types of water quality more likely to exhibit functionality.

The scatter plot effectively examined RQ 2, revealing no correlation, which was further supported by linear regression analysis. Contrary to the initial assumption and prevailing literature, the findings suggest that as water altitude increases, the water production also increases. However, it is important to note the lack of significance in this finding, indicated by the low Pearson coefficient of 0.05 and the shallow slope of the linear regression line. These factors lead to the conclusion that the observed relationship was likely due to chance rather than being definitive based on the data.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Summary

In conclusion, this research explored diverse pre-processing methods for data set variations to develop classification models with varied performance. Different approaches were employed in feature selection and engineering and four classification models were considered. Visual data analysis provided preliminary findings related to the research question, which were solidified through ML and statistical analysis. The Random Forest classifier outperformed other models, achieving 92% and 83% accuracy for Ali and Bukhari, respectively, in predicting water point functionality. Encoding procedures were

identified as the primary factor causing performance differences. Varying cardinalities resulting from different encoding methods led to inferior performance in the higher cardinality data set.

The answers to RQ 1 and 2 were inconclusive due to low Pearson coefficients, indicating chance correlations. However, RQ 1a findings were more conclusive and supported the initial hypothesis.

B. Short Comings

The study's methodology exhibited limited diversity, particularly in addressing missing values in placeholders. This approach was insufficiently thorough. It is noteworthy that Ali's data set introduced bias due to the utilization of tree-based feature selection based on RF.

Consequently, the research questions were supported by weak evidence, resulting in unremarkable outcomes. The Naive Bayes classification model's performance was notably lower, achieving only 50% for Bukhari's data set, compared to the literature reviews and other examined models.

These interconnected issues emphasize the necessity for a more comprehensive methodology that effectively handles missing values and mitigates bias in feature selection. Enhancing the validity of research findings and enabling more accurate and insightful outcomes in future investigations requires careful consideration of these factors.

C. Future Suggestions

Further research is recommended to determine the optimal water quality for addressing RQ 1a. Although the impact of water quality on functionality is confirmed, specific factors yielding the best results require further investigation perhaps to determine the best and worst type of water qualities for water point functionality.

Expanding the range of classification models provides clearer insights, especially when models based on the same principles show similar performances. This enhances comprehensiveness and enables more robust conclusions.

Mitigate bias in classification model performance, feature selection should be conducted using a model not evaluated in the report.

Conducting multiple ML and statistical analyses per research question as, opposed one, could yield more interesting and significant results. This approach ensures fair answers by considering various analytical approaches.

Limiting feature selection methods to avoid high cardinality data sets. This would promote higher CM accuracy scores.

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